

PREVENTING ZOMBIES AND OTHER CHALLENGES

REBECCA E. NORDQUIST

PUBLISHED ON EDUBLOGS ON MAY

<https://rebeccanordquist.edublogs.org/>

LICENSING CC-BY-LC

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15396774

Sitting in a waiting lounge on the way to a far away destination, my partner looked over at what I was reading and burst out laughing. It took some time to convince him that this is a serious paper I was reading, with a subtitle of “**How to prevent zombies?**” (de la Croix & Veen, 2018)... But despite the title that brings out images of the Walking Dead, the underlying message is serious. If we want to stimulate deep learning, how do we construct teaching and learning so that students aren’t just parroting back another bunch of words and terms that “fit the bill” when we ask students to write a reflection?

Dolls in a storefront window with blank stares and hands reaching out.... have they become reflexive zombies???

This problem exists now even more than in 2018, when the Reflective Zombie opinion piece was published, as we now also have created our own bionic zombies with Generative AI. As educators we are all trying to find our bearings in this new reality- my university, as many others, has started to put together guidelines and discussion areas, some of which [can be found here](#). The intrusion of generative AI (and yes, it still feels like an intrusion) into education has led to heated discussions between the educators who look to harness AI as a learning aid (Krause et al., 2025; Lin et al., 2025) and those who are more skeptical (Giannakos et al., 2024). I find myself in the latter camp, with the sceptics, because of both ethical concerns related to what genAI spits out and why and because I feel students miss important experiences when GenAI writes for them.

In the end both of the biological and cyber zombie sources have similar challenges and potential solutions in teaching. Discussing drafts along the way. Live contact with students, in question and answer sessions, presentations, oral exams. Encouraging different kinds of reflection than the one-size-fits-all reflective essay: visual arts, music, and other creative forms of reflection can bring much

more meaning to some students that writing. With this comes the longing for more time to spend per student, to teach at a more personal level and allow for individual paths- and fitting that into higher education- the Shrinking Budget Zombie, which may be the most undead of all.

de la Croix, A., & Veen, M. (2018). The reflective zombie: Problematizing the conceptual framework of reflection in medical education. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 7(6), 394–400.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-018-0479-9>

Giannakos, M., Azevedo, Roger, Brusilovsky, Peter, Cukurova, Mutlu, Dimitriadis, Yannis, Hernandez-Leo, Davinia, Järvelä, Sanna, Mavrikis, Manolis, & Rienties, B. (2024). The promise and challenges of generative AI in education. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 0(0), 1–27.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2024.2394886>

Krause, S., Panchal, B. H., & Ubhe, N. (2025). Evolution of Learning: Assessing the Transformative Impact of Generative AI on Higher Education. *Frontiers of Digital Education*, 2(2), 1–15.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s44366-025-0058-7>

Lin, C.-J., Lee, H.-Y., Wang, W.-S., Huang, Y.-M., & Wu, T.-T. (2025). Enhancing reflective thinking in STEM education through experiential learning: The role of generative AI as a learning aid.

Education and Information Technologies, 30(5), 6315–6337. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-13072-5>